

CROP AND RESOURCE MANAGEMENT

Soil microbiology and biological N fertilizer

Effect of blue-green algae (BGA) inoculation and urea supergranule (USG) on rice yields in sodic soils

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We studied the effect of BGA inoculation in a sodic soil (pH 9.01, EC 0.33 dS/m, and exchangeable sodium percentage 32) at 4 levels of N (0, 75, 100, and 125% of recommended) applied as USG.

The field experiment was conducted Sep-Jan 1985-86. Plots were 3 × 1.75 m with 3 replications of 8 treatments, in a randomized block design. Soil test

showed the need for 127.5-80-87.5 kg NPK/ ha. All the plots were treated basally with superphosphate (16% P₂O₅), muriate of potash (60% K₂O), and 25 kg ZnSO₄/ha.

Inoculation of BGA significantly increased grain and straw yield over the control and in the treatment with 100% fertilizer N (see table). □

Effect of BGA inoculation on rice grain and straw yield.^a Trichy, India.

N level (%)	Grain yield (t/ha)		% increase	Straw yield (t/ha)		% increase
	Without BGA	With BGA		Without BGA	With BGA	
0	2.0	2.3	15*	4.6	5.4	17*
75	2.6	2.7	ns	6.1	6.8	ns
100	2.9	3.6	12*	7.0	7.9	12*
125	3.3	3.4	ns	7.5	7.7	ns
CD (0.05)	0.2			0.8		

^a* = significant difference, ns = not significant.

Physiology and plant nutrition

Influence of iron on nutrient uptake by rice

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Brazil has about 30 million ha of lowland areas suitable for rice. But after 1 or 2 yr cultivation, Fe toxicity builds up in flooded rice because of a decrease in soil fertility. Nutrient imbalance may be the main cause.

A solution culture experiment with increasing Fe concentrations was conducted to understand the nutrient uptake behavior of lowland rice cultivars. With slight modifications, the nutrient solutions were those developed by IRRI. The macronutrient composition in mM follows: 2.85 NH₄NO₃, 0.13 NaH₂PO₄, 1.03

Table 1. Uptake of nutrients in the roots and shoots of rice cultivars.^a

Nutrient	Fe 0.09 mM		Fe 0.89 mM		Fe 1.78 mM	
	Concn % or ppm	Content (mg or µg/4 plants)	Concn % or ppm	Content (mg or µg/4 plants)	Concn % or ppm	Content (mg or µg/4 plants)
<i>Roots</i>						
N	2.82 a	23 a	2.76 a	11 b	2.53 b	6 b
P	0.33 ab	2.66 a	0.27 b	1 a	0.39 a	0.96 b
K	2.95 a	25 a	1.73 b	6 b	1.46 b	4 b
Ca	0.08 a	0.65 a	0.10 a	0.38 b	0.11 a	0.26 c
Mg	0.12 a	1 a	0.11 b	0.42 b	0.11 a	0.26 b
Zn	44 a	37 a	26 c	10 b	38 b	10 b
Cu	19 b	15 a	22 a	8 b	23 a	6 c
Mn	22 c	18 a	27 b	10 b	38 a	9 b
Fe	2258 c	1806 c	12717 b	4658 b	37458 a	9202 a
<i>Shoots</i>						
N	4.09 b	186 a	3.38 c	51 b	4.18 a	50 b
P	0.48 a	21 a	0.18 c	3 b	0.26 b	3 b
K	2.95 a	133 a	1.94 c	26 b	2.17 b	25 b
Ca	0.17 b	8 a	0.24 a	3 b	0.22 a	3 b
Mg	0.43 a	19 a	0.39 b	5 b	0.22 c	5 b
Zn	24 a	109 a	18 c	24 b	21 b	25 b
cu	14 b	62 a	16 ab	22 b	17 a	20 b
Mn	199 a	874 a	139 c	183 b	152 b	184 b
Fe	350 c	1578 c	2008 b	2627 b	4233 a	4988 b

^aValues are mean of 12 cultivars. Concentrations of macronutrients are in % and micronutrients in ppm. Similarly, macronutrient contents are in mg and micronutrients in µg. Under each Fe level, values for each nutrient followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 0.05 level by Duncan's multiple range test.

K₂SO₄, 1 CaCl₂, 1.64 MgSO₄·7H₂O. Micronutrient composition in µM is 9.1 Mn as MnCl₂·4H₂O, 0.52 Mo as

(NH₄)₆Mo₇O₂₄·4H₂O, 18.48 B as H₃BO₃, 0.15 Zn as ZnSO₄·7H₂O, and 0.16 Cu as CuSO₄·5H₂O. Fe was